

THERMAL AND ULTRASONICS DAMAGE MONITORING AND CHARACTERIZATION IN WOVEN COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The interest for woven composites keeps increasing in the aeronautic industry. Compared to classic unidirectional laminates, these materials present several substantial advantages: they can be used to design complex-shaped structures at low manufacturing costs, they have better damage tolerance properties and a higher out-of-plane stress resistance.

However, an accurate modeling of their damage mechanisms is much more complex, since they occur at several scales [1]: fiber cracking (micro-scale), intra-yarn cracking (meso-scale), matrix cracking, matrix/yarn and yarn/yarn debonding (macro-scale). A promising approach could be to develop a multi-scale model, based on the discrete insertion of cracks into the mesoscopic intact mesh of a composite cell [2].

Experimental data is obviously needed, in order to improve and validate such a model, and rises multiple expectations, in terms of:

- damage *detection* and *identification*;
- damage *severity* estimation;
- damage *effects* quantification on mechanical properties.

It seems that a relevant *in situ* multi-instrumentation of mechanical tests could bring valuable data. In this context, an experimental campaign was carried out in Onera, for a 2D glass-fiber epoxy woven composite, manufactured with an RTM (*Resin Transfer Moulding*) process [3]. The chosen epoxy resin was the RTM-6, from Hexcel[®].

The aim of the present paper is to highlight the contribution of two non-destructive techniques, passive infrared thermography and guided waves monitoring, that were used during these mechanical tests.

Once the experimental setup is detailed (Section 2), results from thermal monitoring (Section 3) and ultrasonics monitoring (Section 4) are discussed. In both cases, the link with mechanical data is initiated, and comparisons are made with other independent experimental monitoring techniques, such as digital image correlation, acoustic emission and/or micrographic observations.

2 Multi-instrumentation for the mechanical tests

The tested samples are 185 mm long, 25 mm wide, and constituted of four plies of 2D glass-fiber epoxy woven composite, so that their total thickness is 1.6 mm (Fig. 1). Once in the machine grips, the observable field is a 100×25 mm² rectangular zone.

Fig. 1. Initial composite plate and tested samples (*left*); micrographic observation of an edge (*right*).

The performed tests are tensile tests, monotonic or with pauses at constant loads, all carried out on a 150 kN Zwick mechanical machine with a 0.5 mm/mn displacement speed, and monitored by several independent techniques (Fig. 2).

The monotonic loading phases can be monitored by passive thermography, digital image correlation and acoustic emission or guided waves. These two latter techniques were not used at the same time, for

compatibility issues. As for the steps at constant loads, inspections by active thermography can be carried out, as long as characterization by guided waves; moreover, a polished free edge of the tested sample can be observed with the optical microscope (Fig. 3).

Fig.2. Global experimental setup (*up*); zoom on the sample (*bottom*).

Fig.3. Monitoring of a step-loading tensile test, during loading phases (*up*) and while the test is stopped at constant load (*bottom*).

The thermal monitoring is ensured by a CEDIP Jade III long-wave infrared camera, covering a spectral range from 7.7 to 9.3 μm , with a 320×240 px space resolution and a 20 mK NETD (*Noise Equivalent Temperature Difference*). When the test is paused, two Elinchrom flash lamps, which generate a 12 kJ thermal pulse in 4 ms, can be used for inspections by pulse thermography.

As illustrated by Figure 2, the face of the sample at which the infrared camera points is blackened with a peelable painting.

The opposite face of the sample, covered with a black and white Speckle pattern, is observed by a digital image correlation system, constituted of two 4 Mpx resolution CCD cameras.

The ultrasonics monitoring, which is based on the measurement of time-of-flights of a guided wave, for a given Lamb mode, requires the use of two circular piezoelectric discs (of a 10 mm diameter): the first one is used as an emitter; the second one as a receiver.

An acoustic emission sensor (Pac Nano 30) is also fixed at the bottom of the sample, with a 20 dB detection threshold.

The micrographic images of the edge of the sample are obtained with a 1.4 Mpx resolution CCD camera, coupled to an Olympus optical microscope, through a $\times 5$ objective.

3 *In situ* thermal monitoring

Passive thermography is used during all loading phases. The followed approach is twofold:

- monitoring of the mean temperature of the sample, averaged over the observation zone;
- imaging and identifying the damage;
- assessment of the local released heat associated with every damage.

A 200 Hz frequency is used for the acquisition, in order to avoid the risk to miss any major thermal discontinuity which should match with a damage.

In this section, a step-loading tensile test, constituted of four loadings (0 \rightarrow 40 MPa; 40 \rightarrow 50 MPa; 50 \rightarrow 60 MPa; 60 \rightarrow 80 MPa), is studied (Fig. 4). The results, obtained by the thermal passive monitoring, are detailed for the third tensile loading.

Fig.4. Sequence of loadings.

3.1 Mean temperature monitoring

The mean sample temperature is initialized to zero at the beginning of each loading, so that the actual studied quantity is the global temperature gradient ΔT_{mean} generated by the mechanical testing. Assuming that the mean thermal properties of the material remain uniform and constant, the temperature is expected to vary inversely proportionally to the stress along the direction y of the loading (as long as the stress variations in the two other directions can be negligible):

$$\Delta T_{\text{mean}} = -\frac{\alpha_{\text{th}} T_0}{\rho c_p} \Delta \sigma_y \quad (1)$$

with α_{th} the thermal expansion coefficient, T_0 the initial mean temperature before the test starts, ρ the density of the material, and c_p its specific heat. $\Delta \sigma_y$ is the stress variation in the loading direction, which is, for these tests, the wrap direction.

Therefore, during a tensile loading, as long as the tested sample remains undamaged, ΔT_{mean} should decrease linearly. When damage mechanisms are engaged, this thermoelastic behavior should no longer be seen and be replaced by several thermal discontinuities, each one of them being the consequences of cracks inside the sample.

Figure 5 confirms this prediction for the tensile loading between 50 MPa and 60 MPa. The first damage event appears quickly (for $\Delta \sigma_y \approx 2$ MPa), which can be explained by the fact that the sample was previously damaged in the first two loadings. However, after this isolated event, a linear decrease is indeed checked, until $\Delta \sigma_y \approx 6$ MPa, when several thermal discontinuities are detected. These events testify of the presence of macro or meso-scale damage, such as matrix or yarn cracking.

Fig.5. Time evolutions of the mean stress (*up*) and temperature (*bottom*) during a tensile loading.

3.2 Imaging and identifying the damage

Once the time detection of the thermal events is done, the associated local temperature variations can be studied. In order to highlight the damage effect on the local temperature field and to improve its space location (in the $\{x, y\}$ plane), the difference with the image right before is observed. The damage is then isolated and the contrast of the thermal image is much better (Fig. 6). This operation is based on the assumption that the surface signature of the damage event is an instantaneous phenomenon, which seems sensible given the high acquisition frequency that was chosen.

The appearance of damage generates local temperature increases of a few hundreds mK, which is in good agreement with the mean temperature variation monitored in Figure 5. In the present case, for this particular tensile loading, the maximal relative temperature amplitude induced by damage does not exceed half a degree. It is also observed for the other loadings, except for the final rupture for which a greater local temperature rise is recorded.

The imaging of the damaged zones is quite time-consuming, since it requires to select the pertinent observation times. In order to simplify and speed up this process, an automatic procedure was set. Based on the principle of the TSR (*Thermographic Signal Reconstruction*) data processing technique [4], which is commonly used for non-destructive inspection, the time-evolution of the temperature of each pixel is fitted by a logarithmic polynomial of degree 7. Then the image of the highest-order

coefficient image is studied. This technique leads to spectacular results when applied to flash thermography experiments, since the time-evolution of the temperature is expected to have a $-1/2$ slope in a log/log scale [5]. Applied to damage monitoring, it also provides a very satisfactory, rapid overview of the areas that are damaged during the tensile loading (Fig. 7). Indeed, even though the quality of the regression is poor, the difference between undamaged and damaged pixels can still be made.

Fig.6. Local temperature increases and thermal differential images for three damage events.

Fig.7. Polynomial regression image processing of the thermal images for each of the tensile loadings.

The main advantage of this processing technique is that the resulting image is synthetic: all detected

damages are visible on one unique image. On the other hand, two major drawbacks can be underlined: the information in time is lost, and the color difference from one damage to another does not have a physics explanation (these images do not show temperature fields anymore, but only variations of mathematics functions used for the regression).

For all tensile loadings, the thermal fields associated with the damage events are quite identical: they show what seems to be matrix cracking or matrix/yarn debonding, which would have spread all along the width of the sample, in the direction orthogonal to the loading direction. In order to formally identify the nature of the damage, comparisons with microscopic observations on the polished free edge of the sample, recorded during the 60 MPa load pause, are made (Fig. 8).

Fig.8. Cracks detected both on microscopic images of the polished free edge of the sample (*left*) and on thermal images (*right*).

Since the optical microscope scans the edge of the sample with a 2.4 mm vertical displacement between every image, which ensures an overlap of 100 px, it is possible to rebuild the image of the whole edge,

and then to select one particular image for a given y-position, so that one thermal event can be precisely linked to a microscopic image. Figure 8 illustrates the results for the three previously studied damage events (Fig. 6): matrix cracking is indeed identified.

The analysis of these microscopic images gives another meaningful piece of information: the cracks are oriented almost exclusively along the material thickness, which makes them almost impossible to detect by classic non-destructive techniques, such as flash thermography (Fig. 9). Indeed, the rupture of thermal properties, which is usually detected when delaminations occur in a composite laminate, is much lighter. In a previous study, it was however shown that advanced operations on the image resulting from the difference between two consecutive steps could eventually lead to a detection of some (not all) of the cracks [6]. Further investigation is still under progress in Onera, a significant research effort being currently led in the potential of the vibrothermography technique to detect such cracks.

Fig.9. Inspection of the sample by pulse thermography, at the 50 MPa and 60 MPa steps. Comparison with the synthetic image obtained after the intermediate loading.

These microscopic images are also used to count the number of cracks that appear from one constant-load step to another, and to give their longitudinal positions. Ultimately, it leads to the cracking kinetics (Fig. 10), which is crucial data for the mechanical prediction models. In the present case, it appears, as it was seen on the thermal fields, that the sample damage starts from the very first tensile loading, and speeds up from the second loading. The number of cracks then seems to increase almost linearly. As for the longitudinal positions of the cracks, they are basically uniformly distributed along the sample edge.

Fig.10. Cracking kinetics for the sample, submitted to four consecutive tensile loadings.

Finally, in order to confirm the in-plane location of the damage, a qualitative comparison is carried out between thermal images and the out-of-plane strain fields given by digital image correlation. Due to the low frequency initially chosen for the acquisition of the strain field images (1 image every 2 seconds), the comparisons are not easy to make: several cracks may be visible on only one strain field image. However, based on the y-positions of the cracks and on their spatial extents, a fine agreement is found between the instantaneous variations of the out-of-plane strain $\Delta\epsilon$ and of the temperature ΔT (Fig. 11).

Fig.11. Comparisons between strain fields acquired by digital image correlation on one face of the sample (*up*) and thermal fields acquired by passive thermography on the opposite face (*bottom*).

3.3 Heat assessment

The final step of the thermal data processing is the quantitative assessment of the heat q_{damage} generated by the damage and detected in surface. Assuming that the thermal effusivity b_z of the material remains constant along the thickness direction, this quantity is directly proportional to the local temperature gradient ΔT_{damage} [7]:

$$q_{\text{damage}} \propto b_z \sqrt{t} \Delta T_{\text{damage}} \quad (2)$$

This quantity, for which instantaneous or cumulative values can be considered, appears to be a relevant damage parameter and a pertinent complement for the acoustic emission data. In the three following figures (Fig. 12 to 14), data are normalized by the highest value recorded during the tensile loading.

Fig.12. Normalized instantaneous heat and acoustic energy values.

Fig.13. Normalized cumulative heat and acoustic energy values.

A closer look at Figure 12 enables to draw the following conclusions:

- as expected, the number of acoustic peaks is much higher than the number of thermal peaks: all thermal events are detected by acoustic emission, but only the acoustic peaks of the highest energies are detected by passive thermography (an acoustic energy threshold above which the damage is seen

on the thermal fields can be defined); this is in good agreement with the previous observations, which already validated the fact that only meso/macro-scale damage is detected by passive thermography;

- except for three highly energetic acoustic peaks which are not associated with thermal signatures, which is explained by the fact the cracks occurred outside the observation window (inside the grips or under the acoustic emission piezoelectric sensor), it seems that when a damage generates an acoustic signal of high energy, it also releases a significant heat quantity; however, this tendency is not obvious and no simple relation between acoustic energy and heat can be deduced from the present results.

The fact that the variation of the thermal and acoustic signatures are not always in perfect agreement from one given crack to another indicates that these two independent experimental data should be considered together (and not only confronted to each other), so that a "severity" map can be defined, as illustrated by Figure 14. This representation also stresses the fact that for this particular loading, the acoustic signatures are higher than the thermal ones.

Fig.14. "Severity" map, designed for every damage detected by passive thermography, based on the generated acoustic energy and the released heat.

Finally, the visualization of the time-evolution of the cumulative data, given by Figure 13, underlines the fact that passive thermography should not be used to determine a damage threshold. However, another threshold can be defined, based on the beginning of meso/macro-scale damage.

This notion of "damage threshold", which requires the detection of the first damaging events that occur during the mechanical test, or of their effects, led to complete this study with an ultrasonics monitoring.

4 In situ ultrasonics monitoring

One of the main interests of Lamb waves is that they are guided waves which propagate in the plane with wavelengths that can be selected high enough to explore the tested material at the scale of several woven cells. Consequently, the measurement of their time-of-flights can lead to homogeneous plane mechanical properties.

4.1 Principle of the Lamb waves monitoring

In this study, the tested samples are instrumented with two 10 mm diameter piezoelectric disks. In order to maximize the length of the propagation path, they are fixed at the sample tips, so that they are initially separated by a distance close to 100 mm (Fig. 15).

Fig.15. Schematic of the piezoelectric system used for ultrasonics monitoring.

The choice is made to excite the emitter disk with a single cycle tone burst at a frequency associated with a wavelength equal to twice its diameter (that is to say 20 mm), in order to generate an extension wave, also known as the S_0 Lamb mode. In such a frequency range, the ratio between the sample thickness (1.6 mm) and the wavelength being quite low, this mode can be considered to be non-dispersive, thus associated with a constant velocity v_2 . As long as the sample is undamaged, before any tensile test starts, and under the assumption of an equivalent homogeneous elastic orthotropic material, this velocity can be linked to the elastic plane stress modulus E_2 in the direction y of the loading:

$$v_2 = \sqrt{\frac{E_2}{\rho(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})}} \quad (3)$$

with ν_{12} and ν_{21} the Poisson coefficients.

Let us note here that in a parallel study in Onera, a full characterization of the initial plates was made. Assuming that the woven is perfectly balanced, the Poisson coefficients were considered equal and their values, computed from the ratio between the transverse and the axial strains in the elastic regime, were found close to 0.15 [8]. Thus, for this study, the approximate form of equation (3) will be used, which leads to a very simple expression of the elastic plane stress modulus E_2 :

$$E_2(t) \approx \rho v_2(t)^2 \quad (4)$$

Once the tensile test is started, signals that reach the second piezoelectric disk are recorded every second. The cross-correlation between the excitation signal and the received one leads to the estimation of the time-of-flight τ of the S_0 wave between both disks. The time-evolution of the velocity v_2 during the test can then be deduced:

$$v_2(t) = \frac{l_0(1 + \varepsilon(t))}{\tau(t)} \quad (5)$$

with l_0 the initial distance between the piezoelectric disks and ε the strain which is given by digital image correlation, using a virtual extensometer.

Combining equations (4) and (5) finally gives a direct relation between the time of flight τ and the modulus E_2 [9]:

$$E_2(t) \approx \rho \left(\frac{l_0(1 + \varepsilon(t))}{\tau(t)} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

This procedure was applied to monotonic tensile tests, as well as step-loading tests (with pauses at constant stress levels).

4.2 Monitoring of monotonic tensile tests

Two samples (sample A and sample B), from two composite plates, are tested. In addition to the ultrasonics Lamb waves monitoring, the monotonic tensile loadings are also monitored by passive thermography.

The time-evolutions of the stress and of the mean temperature, averaged over the zone of the samples between the piezoelectric disks, during the tensile loading are given in Figure 16. As explained in the previous section, the slow, linear, decrease of the temperature at the beginning of the test, before any major damage appears, is checked. The detected

thermal discontinuities are in good agreement with the nonlinearities of the stress evolution, and can be linked to meso/macro-scale damage (Fig. 17). It seems that damage appears sooner for sample B, but with a weaker intensity than for sample A.

Fig.16. Time evolutions of the stress and of the mean temperature during the tensile test.

Fig.17. Thermal differential images showing the appearance of some damage events in sample A (up) and sample B (bottom), until final rupture.

The thermal fields associated with the detected damage events are quite similar from one sample to

another. However, the damage patterns are quite different from the ones observed in Section 3. The main damage mechanism seems to be matrix/yarn debonding, rather than matrix cracking. In particular, it should be noted that the local temperature instantaneous variations make the woven texture clearly appear: the yarns oriented in the warp direction (that is to say the loading direction), for which the local instantaneous variations of the plane strains are negative ($\Delta\epsilon_{xx} < 0$; $\Delta\epsilon_{yy} < 0$), see their temperature locally increase ($\Delta T > 0$) when the debonding occurs. The exact opposite phenomenon appears for the yarns oriented in the weft direction. It is particularly noticeable for sample B. A more thorough study, based on the comparison between thermal and digital image correlation fields, is needed on that point.

The variations of the mean temperature with the stress are also plotted in Figure 18, and compared to the ones of the mean plane modulus E_2 , deduced from the S_0 mode time-of-flight measurements.

Fig.18. Variations of the mean temperature and of the axial plane modulus with the stress, during the tensile test.

The analysis of Figure 18 shows that the Lamb waves monitoring is sensitive to early damage, so that a damage threshold can be defined. In the present case, it seems that the damage threshold of sample A is lower than the one of sample B. Once a

15% drop on the modulus is reached, the behavior of both samples become quite similar: a damage saturation level is observed, before the final ruin of the samples, for a 25% drop on the modulus.

4.3 Monitoring of step-loading tensile tests

The tensile testing for sample C is constituted of four loadings, with intermediate pauses at the following constant stress values: 40 MPa, 80 MPa, 120 MPa and 160 MPa. Once again, the monotonic phases of the test are monitoring by passive thermography; when the test is stopped, at a given stress level and at zero loading, ultrasonics measurements are carried out and microscopic images are recorded along the polished free edge of the sample.

The monitoring of the mean temperature during each of the loadings underlines the change of behavior due to the accumulation of damage (Fig. 19). The linear decrease of the temperature is checked before any major damage occurs, but this thermoelastic regime gets shorter and shorter from one loading to another. The temperature profile becomes much more discontinuous and the global temperature decrease amplitude, averaged over the sample, keeps slowing down, due to the heat released by the damage events.

Fig.19. Variations of the mean temperature during the four tensile loadings.

The first significant thermal event is detected at the end of the second loading. It can be assumed that the mechanical properties of the tested material should be considerably altered after that tensile loading, which is indeed checked with the evolution of the

mean axial plane modulus, deduced from the extension wave time-of-flights (Fig. 20): the drop of modulus is close to 20%. Then, after loadings #3 and #4, the decrease of modulus is much lighter, with a final drop of 25% compared to the initial value.

It should also be pointed out that the values found for the mean plane modulus E_2 , are almost identical, whether the time-of-flight measurements are carried out during a loaded state or during an unloaded state. This means that the S_0 Lamb mode is sensitive to the damage, even after its appearance, which is definitely not so clear with infrared thermography.

Fig.20. Evolution of the axial plane modulus from one loaded or unloaded step to another.

These results, from passive thermography and Lamb waves monitoring, are in good agreement with the mechanical data acquired during the test by a force gauge sensor, as illustrated by the successive hysteretic loops of the stress / strain curves (Fig. 21): loadings #1, #3 and #4 do not generate a significant drop of modulus, unlike loading #2.

Fig.21. Stress-strain evolutions from one tensile loading to another.

A fine qualitative agreement is also found with the microscopic images, taken during the constant load pauses: Figure 22 shows the rise of the number of cracks at a given longitudinal position on the edge of the sample, loadings after loadings. It is confirmed that the first cracks appear after the second tensile loading and are detectable at the 80 MPa step.

Fig.22. Microscopic images of the polished free edge of the sample. Comparisons between increasing load steps. Cracks are highlighted in a red color.

5 Conclusions

The present study highlights the relevance of infrared thermography and guided waves, two techniques that are commonly used for nondestructive inspections, for *in situ* damage monitoring.

It was shown that passive thermography, the less intrusive experimental monitoring technique, can lead not only to a better understanding of the major damage mechanisms of woven composites, but also to a quantification of their severity. The interest to couple a global approach, by considering mean quantities such as the averaged sample temperature, to a local approach, by assessing the heat released by

damage like matrix cracking, was pointed out. The comparisons with strain fields from digital image correlation, with acoustic emission energy peaks, and with microscopic visualizations of one edge of the sample (when a step-loading test is carried out) were proven fruitful and should be investigated in future works.

The major drawback of this monitoring technique is that it cannot be used to determine a damage threshold, since it is only sensitive to meso and macro-scale damage. One research prospect that is currently followed in Onera is the opportunity to use vibrothermography during the constant-stress pauses, in order to estimate its sensitivity to early damage events.

As for the ultrasonics monitoring, based on the measurement of the time-of-flights of the extension wave (S_0 Lamb mode), the first results presented in this paper are quite promising. It was shown that this technique leads to a continuous variation of the mean axial tangent modulus, which is much harder to get from mechanical measurements only, and that it can be applied during loadings, as well as when the test is stopped at a constant stress (even at zero loading), which means that it remains sensitive to the damage after its appearance. Moreover, it was pointed out that the variations of the modulus could be used to define (or confirm) a damage threshold.

The one major drawback is that the excitation of the extension mode in such a narrow sample does not enable to estimate, either the plane modulus E_1 in the direction orthogonal to the loading axis, or the out-of-plane modulus E_3 . Other experimental tests are now required: the use of a different Lamb mode, such as the flexural A_0 mode, is to be considered.

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